

SMARANDACHE FUNCTIONS OF THE SECOND KIND

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The Smarandache functions of the second kind are defined in [1] thus:

$$S^k: \mathbf{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbf{N}^*, \quad S^k(n) = S_n(k) \quad \text{for } n \in \mathbf{N}^*,$$

where S_n are the Smarandache functions of the first kind (see [3]).

We remark that the function S^1 has been defined in [4] by F. Smarandache because $S^1 = S$.

Let, for example, the following table with the values of S^2 :

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
$S^2(n)$	1	4	6	6	10	6	14	12	12	10	22	8	26	14

Obviously, these functions S^k aren't monotony, aren't periodical and they have fixed points.

1. Theorem. For $k, n \in \mathbf{N}^*$ is true $S^k(n) \leq n \cdot k$.

Proof. Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_i^{\alpha_i}$ and $S(n) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq t} \{S_{p_i}(\alpha_i)\} = S(p_j^{\alpha_j})$.

Because $S^k(n) = S(n^k) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq t} \{S_{p_i}(\alpha_i k)\} = S(p_r^{\alpha_r k}) \leq kS(p_r^{\alpha_r}) \leq kS(p_j^{\alpha_j}) = kS(n)$
 and $S(n) \leq n$, [see [3]], it results:

$$(1) \quad S^k(n) \leq n \cdot k \quad \text{for every } n, k \in \mathbf{N}^* .$$

2. Theorem. All prime numbers $p \geq 5$ are maximal points for S^k , and

$$S^k(p) = p[k - i_p(k)], \quad \text{where } 0 \leq i_p(k) \leq \left\lfloor \frac{k-1}{p} \right\rfloor$$

Proof. Let $p \geq 5$ be a prime number. Because $S_{p-1}(k) < S_p(k)$, $S_{p+1}(k) < S_p(k)$ [see [2]] it results that $S^k(p-1) < S^k(p)$ and $S^k(p+1) < S^k(p)$, so that $S^k(p)$ is a relative maximum value.

Obviously,

$$(2) \quad S^k(p) = S_p(k) = p[k - i_p(k)] \quad \text{with} \quad 0 \leq i_p(k) \leq \left\lfloor \frac{k-1}{p} \right\rfloor.$$

$$(3) \quad S^k(p) = pk \quad \text{for} \quad p \geq k.$$

3. Theorem. *The numbers kp , for p prime and $p > k$ are the fixed points of S^k .*

Proof. Let p be a prime number, $m = p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_t^{\alpha_t}$ be the prime factorization of m and $p > \max\{m, k\}$. Then $p_i \alpha_i \leq p_i^{\alpha_i} < p$ for $i \in \overline{1, t}$, therefore we have:

$$S^k(m \cdot p) = S[(mp)^k] = \max_{1 \leq i \leq t} \{S_{p_i^{\alpha_i}}, S_p(k)\} = S_p(k) = kp.$$

For $m=k$ we obtain:

$$S^k(kp) = kp \quad \text{so that} \quad kp \text{ is a fixed point.}$$

4. Theorem. *The functions S^k have the following properties:*

$$S^k = o(n^{1+\varepsilon}), \quad \text{for} \quad \varepsilon > 0$$

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S^k(n)}{n} = k.$$

Proof. Obviously,

$$0 \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S^k(n)}{n^{1+\varepsilon}} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n^k)}{n^{1+\varepsilon}} \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{kS(n)}{n^{1+\varepsilon}} = k \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n)}{n^{1+\varepsilon}} = 0 \quad \text{for}$$

$$S = o(n^{1+\varepsilon}), \quad [\text{see}[4]].$$

Therefore we have $S^k = o(n^{1+\varepsilon})$, and:

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S^k(n)}{n} = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S(n^k)}{n} = \lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow \infty \\ p \text{ prime}}} \frac{S(p^k)}{p} = k$$

5. Theorem. [see[1]]. The Smarandache functions of the second kind standardise $(\mathbf{N}^*, \cdot)$ in $(\mathbf{N}^*, \leq, +)$ by:

$$\Sigma_3: \max\{S^k(a), S^k(b)\} \leq S^k(ab) \leq S^k(a) + S^k(b)$$

and $(\mathbf{N}^*, \cdot)$ in $(\mathbf{N}^*, \leq, \cdot)$ by:

$$\Sigma_4: \max\{S^k(a), S^k(b)\} \leq S^k(ab) \leq S^k(a) \cdot S^k(b) \text{ for every } a, b \in \mathbf{N}^*$$

6. Theorem. The functions S^k are, generally speaking, increasing. It means that:

$$\forall n \in \mathbf{N}^* \exists m_0 \in \mathbf{N}^* \text{ so that } \forall m \geq m_0 \Rightarrow S^k(m) \geq S^k(n)$$

Proof. The Smarandache function is generally increasing, [see [4]], it means that :

$$(3) \quad \forall t \in \mathbf{N}^* \exists r_0(t) \in \mathbf{N}^* \text{ so that } \forall r \geq r_0 \Rightarrow S(r) \geq S(t)$$

Let $t = n^k$ and $r_0 = r_0(t)$ so that $\forall r \geq r_0 \Rightarrow S(r) \geq S(n^k)$.

Let $m_0 = \left[\sqrt[k]{r_0} \right] + 1$. Obviously $m_0 \geq \sqrt[k]{r_0} \Leftrightarrow m_0^k \geq r_0$ and $m \geq m_0 \Leftrightarrow m^k \geq m_0^k$.

Because $m^k \geq m_0^k \geq r_0$ it results $S(m^k) \geq S(n^k)$ or $S^k(m) \geq S^k(n)$.

Therefore

$$\forall n \in \mathbf{N}^* \exists m_0 = \left[\sqrt[k]{r_0} \right] + 1 \text{ so that}$$

$$\forall m \geq m_0 \Rightarrow S^k(m) \geq S^k(n) \text{ where } r_0 = r_0(n^k)$$

is given from (3).

7. Theorem. The function S^k has its relative minimum values for every $n = p!$, where p is a prime number and $p \geq \max\{3, k\}$.

Proof. Let $p! = p_1^{t_1} \cdot p_2^{t_2} \cdots p_m^{t_m} \cdot p$ be the canonical decomposition of $p!$, where $2 = p_1 < 3 = p_2 < \cdots < p_m < p$. Because $p!$ is divisible by $p_j^{t_j}$ it results $S(p_j^{t_j}) \leq p = S(p)$ for every $j \in \overline{1, m}$.

Obviously,

$$S^k(p!) = S[(p!)^k] = \max_{1 \leq j \leq m} \left\{ S(p_j^{k \cdot t_j}), S(p^k) \right\}$$

Because $S(p_j^{k \cdot t_j}) \leq kS(p_j^{t_j}) < kS(p) = kp = S(p^k)$ for $k \leq p$, it results that we have

$$(4) \quad S^k(p!) = S(p^k) = kp, \text{ for } k \leq p$$

Let $p!-1 = q_1^{i_1} \cdot q_2^{i_2} \cdots q_t^{i_t}$ be the canonical decomposition for $p!-1$, then $q_j > p$ for $j \in \overline{1, t}$.

It follows $S(p!-1) = \max_{1 \leq j \leq t} \{S(q_j^{i_j})\} = S(q_m^{i_m})$ with $q_m > p$.

Because $S(q_m^{i_m}) > S(p) = S(p!)$ it results $S(p!-1) > S(p!)$.

Analogous it results $S(p!+1) > S(p!)$.

Obviously

$$(5) \quad S^k(p!-1) = S[(p!-1)^k] \geq S(q_m^{k \cdot i_m}) \geq S(q_m^k) > S(p^k) = kp$$

$$(6) \quad S^k(p!+1) = S[(p!+1)^k] > k \cdot p$$

For $p \geq \max\{3, k\}$ out of (4), (5), (6) it results that $p!$ are the relative minimum points of the functions S^k .

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